

Decision-Making Strategies in Instructional Supervision and its Effectiveness

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Publication Date: 2025/01/24

Abstract

This study aimed to examine the decision-making strategies employed by school heads in the secondary schools of Bacacay Districts for the school year 2023 to 2024, as perceived by the teachers. It also evaluated the effectiveness of these strategies from the perspective of secondary teachers. The study addressed several specific questions: 1. What decision-making strategies do school heads use in instructional supervision? 2. How frequently are these strategies practiced in areas such as analytical, command, collaborative, expertise, and consensus-based decision-making? 3. Are there significant differences in the level of practice of these strategies among the three Bacacay districts? 4. How effective are the strategies in the mentioned areas? 5. What factors influence the decision-making strategies in instructional supervision? 6. What activity proposal can be developed to address the factors affecting decision-making? The null hypothesis, stating no significant difference in the level of practice of decision-making strategies among the districts, was tested using the F-test at a 0.05 significance level. The study used a descriptive-survey methodology with a comparative design, focusing on exploring differences in decision-making practices among the three Bacacay districts. The study involved a population of 284 secondary teachers, with a 92.76% response rate, resulting in 269 valid responses. Statistical methods used for analysis included frequency counts, percentages, weighted means, rankings, and the F-test.

I. INTRODUCTION

The world is continually evolving, prompting nations to reform their educational systems to equip young people with the knowledge and skills required for this dynamic environment. Consequently, the roles of school leaders have undergone significant shifts. They are now expected to act as strategic and transformational leaders, capable of managing extensive educational reforms and driving substantial improvements in educational outcomes.

In this new and demanding environment, the schools and educational leaders are expected to do bigger jobs and deliver more outcomes. The decentralization in many educational systems which provides more school autonomy brings a lot of positive opportunities as well as challenges as well. School accountability as a pillar of school governance is putting a great deal of responsibility on school heads aside from the use of innovative pedagogical processes to achieve excellent student results.

The changes in school administration are part of a larger trend in the management of public and private schools that lead school leaders to learn, unlearn, and re-learn knowledge and skills in school management and supervision. These transformations in educational

landscapes are also happening in the country which redefines school leadership and decision-making in instructional supervision.

The 1987 Philippine Constitution establishes the foundation of the nation's education system and guarantees every citizen's right to quality education at all levels. Section 1, Article XIV specifically mandates the State to uphold and promote this right, ensuring education is accessible to everyone.

In response to the shifts brought about by globalization, the integration of international educational frameworks, and the implementation of the K to 12 program, the Department of Education (DepEd) has updated its standards for school leadership. This led to the revitalization of the National Competency-Based Standards for School Heads (NCBS-SH) and the issuance of DepEd Order No. 24, series of 2020, also known as the National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH). These updates aim to align school leadership with the evolving educational landscape and equip school heads to effectively meet their expanded roles and responsibilities.

The culture and structure of the school organization indeed affect how decisions are crafted, developed, and implemented. The kind of decision-making in instructional supervision that a school leader espouses reflects the kind of leadership and management acumen he or she has. It is often argued that effective decision-making occurs in organizations where members are granted a degree of autonomy in their choices. However, schools in the country are typically structured with closely interconnected internal units, which can restrict individual teachers from making independent decisions. Thus, by their very nature, schools in the Philippines inhibit productive decision-making in instructional supervision; fortunately, with recent paradigm shifts and the empowerment of school heads, multiple solutions are now possible to make decision-making in instructional supervision easy and facilitative.

The researcher is interested in exploring this area because there is a lack of education studies that specifically focus on the softer aspects of management as perceived by secondary teachers in Bacacay Districts. The study delved deeply into the implementation of decision-making strategies in instructional supervision, their effectiveness, and the factors influencing them. Additionally, the study outlined a proposed activity to tackle the factors affecting decision-making strategies and contributed to the existing knowledge in human resource management of schools, aiming to enhance the quality of teaching and learning in Bacacay Districts. Therefore, this study was carried out.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study is grounded in four interconnected theories related to decision-making. These include Herbert Simon's Theory of Decision-Making, Planturroot's Psychological Theory of Supervision, Lev Vygotsky's Collaborative Learning Theory, and Arif Ahmed's Evidential Decision Theory. Additionally, the researcher has developed her own theory based on these four concepts.

Simon (1947) in his Decision-Making Theory stated that making decisions involves choosing between different courses of action, including the option of inaction. He argued that there is never a single best choice, as complete information is unavailable, and thus, multiple options may be considered better at different times. According to Simon, decision-making occurs in three stages: (1) the intelligence activity stage, where problems are identified and the environment is analyzed; (2) the design activity stage, where potential solutions are developed; and (3) the choice activity stage, where alternatives are evaluated, and the most appropriate solution is selected.

Glickman's (1981) Instructional Supervision Theory views educational supervision as a process of directly collaborating with teachers to improve teaching and learning. He suggested that supervisors determine the amount and sequence of direction required based on the developmental needs of teachers, such as their level of commitment and cognitive skills. He identified three types of supervisory orientations: directive, collaborative, and non-directive. In the directive orientation, the supervisor takes a more authoritative role, whereas in the collaborative approach, the supervisor works alongside the teacher in

planning actions. In the non-directive approach, the supervisor observes without interpretation and allows the teacher to self-analyze.

Lev Vygotsky's (1934) Collaborative Learning Theory is based on his concept of the Zone of Proximal Development, where individuals within a group share knowledge and expertise to learn from each other. In a collaborative learning environment, group members work together to solve problems, learn new ideas, or complete tasks. This method fosters a sense of belonging and encourages employees to feel valued within the organization, which increases their engagement and retention.

Lastly, the Analytical Theory by Ekstein & Wallerstein (1963) outlines four stages in instructional supervision: the opening stage, the mid-stage, the working stage, and the final stage. During the opening stage, the teacher and school head assess each other's strengths and weaknesses. The mid-stage is marked by conflict, defensiveness, or avoidance, which is resolved as they move to the working stage. In the final stage, the supervisor adopts a more passive role, encouraging teachers to develop their independence.

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This study, titled Decision-making Strategies and Effectiveness in Bacacay Districts, follows a systems approach, viewing the research as an integrated system consisting of three main components: inputs, process, and output.

The input elements of this study include the decision-making strategies used by school heads in instructional supervision, the level at which these strategies are practiced across five areas (analytical, command, collaborative, expertise, and consensus-based), the effectiveness of these strategies, and the factors influencing decision-making by school heads. The process involves several stages: preparing the research instrument, validating the tool, distributing the questionnaire to the respondents, and retrieving the completed forms. The researcher, with guidance from the Thesis Adviser, created the research tool, which underwent two phases of validation—face and content validation.

A request to conduct the study was submitted to the Schools Division Superintendent of Albay, who provided a letter of authorization for both the study and the external validators suggested during the Proposal Defense. The external validators reviewed the research tool and offered feedback, which was incorporated into the final version. The researcher then personally administered the questionnaire to the secondary teachers of Bacacay Districts, after seeking permission from her school head to visit the island schools for two days. Once the completed questionnaires were retrieved, the responses were compiled in a Master Tally Sheet and analyzed using statistical methods. The findings were presented in tables and discussed in detail.

The output of the study is an activity proposal designed to address the factors that impact the decision-making strategies of school heads. A feedback loop is included in

the study's conceptual model to complete the system and reflect the research process as a continuous cycle.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a descriptive-survey methodology. It is descriptive in nature because it aims to identify the decision-making strategies practiced by school heads and evaluate the effectiveness of these strategies. According to Vizcarra (2003), descriptive studies are valuable for understanding the current state or condition of a problem, which is important for analyzing both past and future situations. This method gathers comprehensive and factual data to describe the existing phenomena.

Sanchez (1998) also supports this approach, noting that descriptive research includes all studies focused on presenting facts about the nature and status of the subject under investigation. The study employed a survey design, utilizing a questionnaire to collect data. Additionally, it followed a comparative design to examine the significant differences in the practice of decision-making strategies across the three districts of Bacacay, while also identifying the factors influencing these strategies.

V. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURES

The study by Lyonga (2018) aimed to explore the impact of head teachers' instructional supervision practices on teacher performance in selected primary schools in Konye Sub-Division, Cameroon. Using a descriptive survey design, the study examined how classroom visits and the review of teaching logbooks influenced teacher performance. The sample included six head teachers and 28 teachers from six schools, comprising state-owned, confessional, and private institutions. Data were collected through a five-section questionnaire administered during a site visit, and SPSS version 20.0 was used for analysis through frequencies and percentages.

The findings highlighted that effective instructional supervision involved not only classroom visits but also observation of teaching methods, examination of teaching strategies, regular review of teachers' records, correction of lesson plans, and guidance sessions with teachers to improve teaching and learning activities. Effective supervision allowed for identifying strengths and areas for improvement, ultimately enhancing teacher performance. The study concluded that strong instructional supervision positively impacts teacher performance.

The current research shares similarities with Lyonga's work in focusing on instructional supervision practices and employing a descriptive survey design with data analysis using frequencies and percentages. However, it differs in its outcomes; while the prior study examined the impact of instructional supervision on primary teacher performance, the current study proposed an activity plan to address factors influencing decision-making strategies in instructional supervision.

Sotomayor's (2022) phenomenological study sought to understand the experiences of Filipino teachers in the UAE regarding instructional supervision and pedagogical

practices. Semi-structured interviews were conducted, guided by a structured questionnaire, to collect consistent data. Key challenges identified included improving learning outcomes, selecting suitable teaching models, addressing student expectations, and integrating academic technology. Teachers employed strategies such as offering student choices, setting clear learning objectives, connecting to students' interests, ensuring relevance, and displaying enthusiasm. The study emphasized the role of school principals in motivating teachers to overcome challenges and innovate in instructional practices.

While the current research and Sotomayor's study both address instructional supervision practices, they differ in methodology and focus. The phenomenological approach in Sotomayor's work involved semi-structured interviews to capture teachers' lived experiences, whereas the current research employed a descriptive survey. Additionally, Sotomayor's study focused on coping mechanisms for challenges in instructional supervision, while the present work emphasized decision-making strategies.

Sule et al. (2015) investigated the relationship between instructional supervisory practices and teacher effectiveness in public secondary schools in Calabar South, Nigeria. Using an ex-post facto design, the study sampled 195 teachers from six schools through random sampling and collected data via structured questionnaires. Findings revealed significant positive relationships between classroom observation, lesson note review, and teacher effectiveness. The study emphasized the need for consistent and thorough supervision to adapt to curriculum changes and recommended government-organized training for principals and teachers.

This study aligns with the present research in examining instructional supervision practices in secondary schools and using questionnaires for data collection. However, it diverges by focusing on the relationship between supervision and teacher effectiveness, while the present research explored decision-making strategies. Moreover, the sampling techniques differed, with the previous study using random sampling and the current research utilizing total population enumeration.

Chiwamba's (2019) study examined teachers' and school heads' understanding and execution of instructional supervision roles in public secondary schools in Tanzania. Employing a mixed-methods approach, it analyzed data from 171 participants through questionnaires, interviews, and document reviews. Findings showed that while school heads understood their roles, they often failed to execute key responsibilities like reviewing lesson plans and professional records. About 68.5% of teacher performance was attributed to factors like supervision of records, professional development, resource provision, and classroom observation. Recommendations included enhanced monitoring mechanisms and capacity-building programs for school heads.

The present study is similar to Chiwamba's in its focus on instructional supervision practices in secondary schools. However, it differs in methodology and scope. While Chiwamba employed a mixed-methods approach with

diverse data collection tools, the current study used a descriptive survey with questionnaires. Additionally, Chiwamba's study examined the understanding of supervision roles and their influence on teacher performance, aspects not covered in the present research.

VI. FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Findings

➤ *The Important Findings of the Study Are:*

A total of 269 secondary teachers participated in the study, with 81 from Bacacay East, 98 from Bacacay South, and 90 from Bacacay West. In Bacacay East, the most commonly practiced decision-making strategy was analytical, followed by consensus-based, command, expertise, and collaborative decision-making. In Bacacay South, analytical decision-making was also the most common, followed by command, expertise, consensus-based, and collaborative decision-making. Similarly, in Bacacay West, analytical decision-making was the most frequently used, followed by command and consensus-based (which tied), expertise, and collaborative decision-making.

The study assessed the level of practice of five decision-making strategies among secondary teachers in Bacacay District. In Bacacay East, the analytical strategy was mainly rated "sometimes," while the command strategy had "always" ratings for controlling decisions. Collaborative decision-making was rated "always" for involving others and generating options. The expertise strategy was mostly rated "often," and the consensus-based strategy showed a mix of "always" and "often" ratings.

In Bacacay South, similar trends were observed, with the analytical and expertise strategies rated "sometimes" and "often," respectively. The command strategy had "always" ratings for decision control, and collaborative decision-making was mostly rated "often." Consensus-based decision-making was rated "always" for developing beneficial agreements.

Bacacay West showed consistent results, with analytical and expertise strategies rated "sometimes" and "often." The command strategy had "always" ratings for decision control, while collaborative decision-making and consensus-based strategies were rated "often," with some indicators rated "always." Overall, decision-making practices were mostly rated between "often" and "always," reflecting a strong application of these strategies in instructional supervision.

The analysis of decision-making strategies, including analytical, command, collaborative, expertise, and consensus-based, showed consistent degrees of freedom across all strategies. For each strategy, the calculated F-values were compared to the tabular F-value. In all cases, the F-values were lower than the tabular value, indicating no significant differences between treatments. As a result, the null hypothesis was rejected, confirming that the decision-making strategies did not differ significantly.

The evaluation of decision-making strategies across Bacacay East, South, and West Districts revealed varying levels of effectiveness. Analytical decision-making was rated as highly effective overall, with notable strengths in time management, teaching-learning enhancement, and learner assessment across all districts. Command decision-making showed moderate effectiveness, particularly excelling in instructional review and time management in Bacacay East, with similar trends observed in the other districts. Collaborative decision-making was rated highly effective, with strengths in building job commitment, goal attainment, and resource utilization. Expertise decision-making was also highly effective, particularly excelling in fostering innovation, enriching the teaching-learning process, and encouraging goal attainment. Lastly, consensus-based decision-making was rated extremely effective overall, standing out in enhancing class management, fostering innovation, and building job commitment. These findings highlight the nuanced effectiveness of each strategy in supporting instructional supervision.

The factors influencing decision-making strategies of school heads across Bacacay East, South, and West Districts varied but showed consistent trends. In analytical decision-making, the top factor was the availability of data and information, followed by the nature of issues for decision-making, and lastly, the school heads' analytical skills. For command decision-making, leadership skills ranked highest, followed by communication skills and personality traits. In collaborative decision-making, the behavior and nature of staff were rated most influential, followed by past experiences of those involved and the quality and quantity of decision-making tools. For expertise decision-making, technical skills of school heads ranked first, followed by social and emotional quotients, and level of expertise. Lastly, in consensus-based decision-making, individual differences among staff members were the most significant factor, while cognitive biases and belief in personal relevance ranked equally as secondary factors. These findings underscore the importance of tailored approaches and specific skills in decision-making processes.

To address the identified decision-making factors, the researcher designed a flexible training program for secondary teachers and school heads, which can be a standalone professional development opportunity or part of in-service training. Considering limited financial resources and participants' time, the training is divided into two components. The first focuses on improving data analysis and technical skills essential for analytical and expertise decision-making. The second addresses leadership, collaboration, and team dynamics, tackling leadership skills, staff behavior, and individual differences in decision-making.

B. Conclusions

➤ *Based on the Above Findings, the Following Conclusions were Drawn:*

- The school heads in Bacacay Districts used different decision-making strategies in instructional supervision and most of them used analytical decision-making

REFERENCES

strategies with less number of school heads that employed collaborative decision-making strategies.

- The school heads of Bacacay Districts sometimes used analytical decision-making and often used command, collaborative, expertise, and consensus-based decision-making strategies.
- There was no significant difference in the level of practice of the decision-making strategies in instructional supervision of school heads along analytical, command, collaborative, expertise, and consensus-based among the three (3) districts.
- The decision-making strategies in instructional supervision of school heads in Bacacay Districts in terms of analytical, command, collaborative, expertise, and consensus-based were effective.
- The factors with the final rank of first in the five (5) decision-making strategies were the following: in analytical is the availability of data and information for analysis to guide decision makers; in command decision-making strategy, the factor was leadership skills of school heads; in collaborative, the factor was behavior and nature of staff; in expertise decision-making, it was: technical skills of school heads and in consensus-based, the factor which has the rank of first was individual differences among staff members and team.
- The activity proposal prepared by the researcher addresses the factors that affect the decision-making strategies in the instructional supervision of school heads.

C. Recommendations

➤ *Based on the Findings and Conclusions, the Researcher Recommends the Following:*

- The Public Schools District Supervisors of Bacacay Districts may offer technical assistance in strengthening the practice of collaborative decision-making strategy so that there will be more school heads who will use this strategy in instructional supervision.
- The school heads be encouraged to practice often as much as possible the analytical decision-making strategy and the other strategies used in this study to a higher level as a community of practice among school heads in the three (3) districts of Bacacay Albay.
- Secondary teachers of Bacacay Districts be trained to use the decision-making strategies in the classroom and motivated to ascertain their effects on the teaching and learning process.
- More efforts must be exerted by the school heads concerning the decision-making strategies they employ in instructional supervision to obtain a very effective level.
- The factors identified in this study that affect the decision-making strategies in instructional supervision be discussed in teachers' meetings for appropriate actions.
- The researcher may furnish the Schools Division Office of Albay with a copy of the activity proposal for consideration.

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